

The concept of network resource control of a 5G cluster focused on the smart city's critical infrastructure needs

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Annotation: The article proposes a concept of organizing access to the guaranteed resource of the 5G cluster information environment, structured in the form of a hierarchy of logical network segments. This framework presents an interrupt access control scheme that exhibits survivability characteristics important to mission-critical applications. Analytically, the author's concept is represented by an irreversible Markov process, for which a system of equilibrium equations and stationary probabilities are defined. Based on the latter, a qualitative metric was formulated, which included such indicators as the average number of requests accepted for service in the 5G cluster, the probability of losing an incoming request, and the average volume of network resource units used in the 5G cluster. For the single input data that characterizes a real NS 5G cluster, a comparison of the author's and known competing access control schemes in terms of formulated qualitative metrics is implemented. The obtained results showed that the author's concept prevails over the competitor in the range of low loads. Note that in this range, the advantage of the author's scheme over the competitor significantly increases with the increase in the number of network segments into which the information environment of the 5G cluster is divided.

Keywords: 5G cluster; information exchange; critical infrastructure; smart city; access control scheme; Markov process; quality metric

1. Introduction

Network Slicing (NS) [1-3] is a technology that allows us to create logical network segments (aka "slices" or "cuts") based on the physical infrastructure of a mobile network. Each network segment is a separate virtual network that can be specifically configured and optimized to meet the requirements of specific applications and services. A typical 5G network logical segment will consist of the following:

- Virtualized Radio Access Network (vRAN) on top of base stations to connect devices to the network;
- Some virtualized network functions of the 5G network core, namely: Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) for managing connections and ensuring device mobility; Session Management Function (SMF) for managing mobile traffic tunnels between the mobile device and the "router", which is the User Plane Function (UPF) for interrupting the mobile tunnel and routing traffic from the device to external networks following policies specified by the user;
- A dedicated port of the core transport network for the connection between the vRAN and the virtualized core network segment.

The exact composition and configuration of the network segment may vary depending on the specific needs of the user. The network segment may not include such 5G core functions as Authentication Server Function (AUSF, subscriber authentication), Unified Data Management (UDM, user profile management), Network Repository Function (NRF, network services and functions catalogue management), etc. Network segments can be dynamically created, modified, and shut down. The functioning of a specific network segment should not affect other network segments and the rest of the network.

How does a mobile device select a network segment? The following options are available:

- Pre-configured selection on the device: pre-configured preferences for selecting one or more network segments;
- Selection of one of the network segments based on information about their characteristics: network performance, the closest point of traffic exit to the public network, cost, etc.;
- User-initiated selection: the user can manually select on his mobile device a specific network segment from the list of available ones on the network;
- The 5G network can "force" connect the device to a suitable network segment based on the settings in the tariff plan, personal account, etc.

Can a mobile device use multiple network segments simultaneously? Of course, it can. For example, one network segment might be used for streaming video with high bandwidth but low jitter requirements, while another network segment could be used for streaming video with low bandwidth but strict jitter requirements. Each application on the device will be given a choice of one or another network segment to access the network.

As we can see, NS is a flexible and productive technology. Naturally, there is a desire to use it to organize and control information communication of various services of the smart city critical infrastructure. For example, controlling traffic lights to regulate city traffic. Let all the smart city traffic lights together produce an insignificant amount of traffic, approximately at the level of one single teenager's smartphone. But the user of traffic lights needs that, regardless of the load on the network, firstly, each traffic light is constantly connected to the network, and secondly, kilobits of traffic light traffic has a higher priority than megabits and gigabits of other types of traffic on the network. Completely different requirements are typical, for example, for

the centralized collection of video content from cameras of a city surveillance system. As a rule, the cameras are equipped with a buffer, which makes it possible to compensate for possible interruptions in the information transfer, but, in any case, the transmission of video materials creates a large load on the network. The only way to organize stable support for such different services in terms of requirements and services in a 5G base station cluster is to use NS technology and create a suitable access control scheme. It is these relevant aspects that our article focuses on.

Over the past five years, the topic of NS applications has been very popular among scientists and engineers working in the field of information and communication technologies. The most compact achievements in this area are presented in surveys [4-8]. These materials describe a range of application approaches, including Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) for implementing various hierarchies of network segments. The value of these surveys also lies in the fact that they describe current problems from the area of research under consideration, as well as provide general statements of problems for promising research. Note that the use of NS to streamline the information exchange of smart city services is also mentioned there.

Studies [9-12] note that the problem of efficient distribution of radio resources (bandwidth or Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs)) is one of the most important when implementing NS technology. Radio resources must be distributed across multiple network segments following the dynamically changing requirements of users and Mobile Virtual Network Operators (MVNOs). At the same time, the key requirements for the isolation of network segments must be met [1, 2].

Theoretical research is focused on the features of specific objects and the reflection of these features in the implementation of the network segments architecture. For example, in the study [13] NFV is mentioned as a key technology. Effective approaches to the formation of such architectures and determining the routing mechanism between individual Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) are described in [14].

In addition to the VNFs responsible for slice selection, research [15] asserts that existing literature emphasizes the necessity of a management system to provision, update, and control the VNFs at the physical layer constituting the network slices. Their focus revolves around the provisioning and deployment of Data Plane Network Slices and the appropriate selection of a slice based on identification parameters from the user equipment. They also verified that deploying traffic control rules can be achieved with minimal resources, ensuring minimal impact on the efficiency of Data Plane slices. As the proposed system advances, a heightened level of automation can be achieved with the integration of a monitoring agent capable of real-time supervision of the traffic status.

The studies in [16, 17] introduced a Network Slice Selection Framework (NSSF) based on the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). Following the principles of network segmentation, mobile users/terminals have the option to select from various connectivity alternatives based on criteria such as slicing performance, service requirements, and user preferences. NSSF represents a logical progression to mobile systems in the 5G era and beyond. NSSF is conceptualized as a Multiple-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) problem, employing the TOPSIS principle to classify available slices based on their attributes and weights. Despite TOPSIS being a widely accepted decision-making tool due to its clear logic, algorithmic approach, and mathematical foundation, it falls short of providing consistent results owing to the issue of rank reversibility.

Regarding TOPSIS methods, the outcomes in [18] indicated that the Standard Deviation weighting technique (SD-TOPSIS) exhibits significantly better performance in addressing rank reversibility, albeit at the expense of increased complexity. Consequently, the authors recommended the adoption of the Entropy weighting technique (E-TOPSIS), particularly when confronted with characteristics such as the fine granularity of slices. The study also emphasized that enhancements in TOPSIS methods are closely linked to alternative approaches for normalization and ranking phases, particularly in practical implementation scenarios. For future investigations, the plan is to scrutinize the impact of various alternative standardization techniques and classification methods on the performance of the NSSF.

Furthermore, findings from [19] encompass the entire decision-making process, including normalization, weighting, and ranking stages. The study reveals that alternative techniques proposed, such as linear normalization, variance weighting, and binary classification alternatives, exhibit a positive impact by notably diminishing classification reversibility and computational complexity across the tested scenarios. These results underscore the significance of considering MCDM methods as a viable solution to the network slice selection challenge in 5G mobile systems and their subsequent generations. For future investigations, there is a call to assess the performance of other MCDM algorithms specifically in terms of ranking reversibility.

The study in [20] introduced a novel approach targeting the enhancement of service utilization and the efficiency of network slices, recognizing slice selection as a pivotal component of 5G NS. In this proposed method, each network slice is treated as a distinct service and is symbolized as a website system with its dedicated database. The GET method is employed to link user equipment to multiple systems concurrently, with a primary focus on transmitting the necessary parameters through the URL. This approach enables Multiple-Service User Equipment (MSUE) to connect simultaneously to several networks, acquiring sessions on the associated networks for a specific duration. For future endeavours, the authors recommend offering users a PURE connection to these networks. In this context, by passing parameters to the new system, users could be registered to all existing systems, leveraging their full capabilities instead of having a temporary connection, as observed in the current work.

Reference [21] introduced a multicriteria decision framework designed for the optimal selection of Edge Points of Presence (EPoPs) in deploying a network slice. The EPoP Selecting Framework consists of three main components: 1) the Service Registry, housing the necessary Key Performance Indicator (KPI) values for each EPoP candidate; 2) the Filtering Engine, responsible for the initial filtering of candidate EPoPs based on user requirements; 3) the PoP Ranking Mechanism, which identifies the most suitable EPoP for slice deployment using the multi-criteria Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process method. The proposed framework underwent evaluation in a realistic scenario, comparing it with simple filtering and the single-object approach. Results highlight the effectiveness of the two-stage method in meeting user requirements for hardware and software, facilitating communication between slices, and optimizing resource allocation from the provider's perspective. Future work is

envisioned to involve the implementation of a distributed selection mechanism aimed at enhancing service discovery and communication between slices, consequently reducing deployment costs.

The study in [22] concentrates on maximizing system resource utilization while ensuring user satisfaction by delving into the End-to-End (E2E) network slicing problem. Through theoretical analysis, the authors demonstrated that this problem falls into the category of NP-hard problems. Subsequently, they introduced a Genetic Algorithm as a solution to the optimization problem. A simulation experiment was undertaken to validate the proposed GA algorithm, revealing superior access and transmission performance compared to traditional selection methods based on Received Signal Strength or greedy algorithms. Although the authors did not explicitly state their intentions for future work, it is reasonable to suggest the execution of real-world experiments utilizing the proposed GA algorithm to corroborate and validate the simulation results obtained in this study.

Reference [23] introduced a solution for 5G network slice selection in Internet of Things (IoT) scenarios, utilizing Edge Computing resources. The approach involved the application of hybrid machine learning algorithms and MCDM methods, allowing IoT applications to better adapt data processing and routing for an enhanced user experience. The results indicated the efficiency of the proposed solution, with the adopted MCDM methods demonstrating similar performance. This underscores the high level of flexibility in ranking alternatives for the proposed methods based on the weights assigned. The authors highlighted the need for future work to explore different scenarios in new experiments, alongside further development in the proposed algorithms. This suggests a commitment to expanding the scope of applicability and refining the efficiency of their approach.

Reference [24] introduced a dynamic slice selection approach by leveraging the learning capability to recognize the current situation and establish mappings between the present scenario and the future slice. The Bayesian Attractor Model (BAM) was employed for consistent recognition, and the Dirichlet Process Mixture Model facilitated automatic attractor construction. Situational mapping was autonomously learned through feedback. The application of dynamic slice selection focused on video streaming situations, revealing that the proposed method effectively maintained high-quality video streaming while minimizing slice changes. An extended BAM was also employed to reduce the frequency of slice changes without significant degradation in video streaming quality. Integration and deletion of attractors were utilized to retain only the essential attractors. For future investigations, the authors suggested incorporating control lag as a parameter into the slice selection prediction mechanism. This emphasizes the importance of considering control lag as part of the dynamic slice selection process to further enhance its predictive capabilities.

An interesting reliability issue is raised in [25], which describes a mechanism for fast switching in the event of a failure of a specific network segment. We also note that most of the studies [26, 27] are devoted to problems and solutions for organizing the network segments architecture based on Radio Access Network (RAN) using the IEEE 802.11 interface.

Note that the specifics of organization and control in critical application-oriented wireless network segment architectures as an independent task in the mentioned studies are not properly disclosed. The authors have not found any research that describes the use of Radio Admission Control (RAC) with interrupts to support shared Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR) access to limited network resources, taking into account the priority of service, reflecting the characteristics of the smart city critical infrastructure traffic organization.

Next, we summarize the main attributes of our research in a compact form.

The *object* of the research is the process of controlling access to the guaranteed resource of the information environment of the 5G cluster, structured in the form of logical network segments hierarchy.

The *subject* of research includes the theory of probability and mathematical statistics, the theory of Markov processes, and the theory of experiment planning.

The *goal* of the research is formulated as follows: to create an effective scheme for controlling access to the 5G cluster, which supports the smart city critical infrastructure information interaction, structured in the form of a logical network segments hierarchy.

Research *objectives* are:

- analytically formalize the studied process with the derivation of the interruption function,
- analytically formalize the concept of controlling network resources of a 5G cluster focused on the smart city critical infrastructure needs,
- analytically determine the main probabilistic characteristics of the research object based on the proposed concept,
- to formulate a qualitative metric for evaluating an arbitrary specimen of the implementation of the research object,
- justify the adequacy of the proposed mathematical apparatus and demonstrate its functionality in the context of the research goal.

The **main contribution** of the research: the article proposes a concept of organizing access to the guaranteed resource of the 5G cluster information environment, structured in the form of a hierarchy of logical network segments. This framework presents an interrupt access control scheme that exhibits survivability characteristics important to mission-critical applications. It is understood that to accept a target request in a network segment, it is allowed to interrupt accepted non-target requests in other network segments, regardless of the priority index of the latter. Analytically, the author's concept is represented by an irreversible Markov process, for which a system of equilibrium equations and stationary probabilities are defined. Based on the latter, a qualitative metric was formulated, which included such indicators as the average number of requests accepted for service in the 5G cluster, the probability of losing an incoming request, and the average volume of network resource units used in the 5G cluster.

2. Models and methods

2.1. Statement of the research

Suppose that the 5G cluster base station functions by distributing R units of the network resource between $V \in \mathbb{N}$ virtual network segments. At the same time, such a separate virtual network segment $v \in V$ monopolistically uses $R_v \leq R$ units of the network resource, $\sum_{v \in V} R_v = R$. We focus the application of our network cluster on serving the smart city's critical infrastructure needs. In this context, we will reserve $G_v < R_v$ units of the network resource for guaranteed access in each v -th virtual network segment (the remaining $R_v - G_v$ units of the network resource will be publicly available). The flow of incoming requests from the elements of the critical infrastructure to the target network segment $v \in V$ is assumed to be Poisson with intensity $\mu_v \in \vec{\mu} = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_V)$.

In the first approximation, the classic Sharing with Maximum Queue Length and Minimum Allocation (SMQLMA) scheme [28] is suitable for describing information and communication interaction in the above-mentioned network cluster. However, the focus on serving the needs of critical infrastructure forces us to pay additional attention to the survivability of information and communication interaction within the entire network cluster. Therefore, in our access scheme with interruptions, we will abandon the strict segregation of incoming requests by address network segment implemented in the SMQLMA scheme (the target network segment is indicated in the incoming request and only it can accept the corresponding request for service).

We assume that a request addressed to another network segment \hat{v} can be accepted for service in the guaranteed access section of the network segment v : s. At the same time, we will provide a protective mechanism: if a targeted request for the service of which a_v units of the resource is required has arrived at the network segment v , but currently there is no such amount of free network resources in either the guaranteed or the publicly accessible sections of the network segment v , then previously accepted non-targeted requests in other network segments $\hat{v} \neq v$ will be interrupted until the volume of the resource, not less than a_v , is released.

Naturally, the smart city critical infrastructure services differ in priority. Taking this fact into account, we will predict the numbering of network segments in descending order of priority (for example, the highest priority will be requests that are served in the network segment with index 1). Let's summarize what has been said in the form of an interruption function

$$\vec{b}(v, \vec{\pi}) = (b_{\hat{v}}(v, \vec{\pi})) = (b_1(v, \vec{\pi}), \dots, b_V(v, \vec{\pi})), \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{\pi} = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_V)$ is a vector, the values of which record the number of received requests in network segments $v \in [1, \dots, V]$. Function (1) determines the number of accepted requests in network segments \hat{v} , which should be interrupted to accept a target request with resource intensity $a_v \in \vec{a}$ in the network segment v (further on, we will consider $a_v = \text{const}$ for the corresponding network segment $v \in V$, $a_v \in \vec{a} = (a_1, \dots, a_V)$).

Therefore, when a request is received to a network segment $v \in V$, one of the following variants of the access control scheme (1) is implemented:

1. If the number of received requests in this network segment is less than $\lfloor R_v/a_v \rfloor$ and the amount of free resources is not less than a_v , then the incoming request will be accepted for service in the network segment v : $(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v - \vec{\Pi}_{\max})\vec{e}_v \leq 0 \wedge (\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v)\vec{a} \leq R$. Here, \vec{e}_v is a row vector of the unit matrix E with dimension $V \times V$; vector $\vec{\Pi}_{\max} = (\lfloor R_1/\pi_1 \rfloor, \dots, \lfloor R_V/\pi_V \rfloor)$ characterizes the maximum possible number of accepted requests $\forall v \in V$;

2. If the number of received requests in the network segment is less than $\lfloor G_v/a_v \rfloor$ and the amount of free resources is less than a_v , then the incoming request will be accepted for service in the network segment v due to the interruption of received non-targeted requests in other network segments $\hat{v} \in V \setminus \{v\}$: $(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v - \vec{\Pi}_G)\vec{e}_v \leq 0 \wedge (\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v - \vec{b}(v, \vec{\pi}))\vec{a} \leq R$. Here, the vector $\vec{\Pi}_G = (\lfloor G_1/\pi_1 \rfloor, \dots, \lfloor G_V/\pi_V \rfloor)$ characterizes the maximum possible number of received requests due to the use of exclusively guaranteed resources of network segments $\forall v \in V$;

3. If the number of accepted requests in this network segment exceeds $\lfloor G_v/a_v \rfloor$ and the amount of free resources is less than a_v , then the incoming request will be lost: $(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v - \vec{\Pi}_G)\vec{e}_v > 0 \wedge (\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v)\vec{a} > R$.

Note that in the defined access control scheme, option 2 is formalized in such a way that it assumes the interruption of received non-target requests \hat{v} with both lower and higher priority relative to the target network segment v .

In general, for $\vec{b}(v, \vec{\pi}) = \vec{0}$, the number of non-target requests $b_{\hat{v}}(v, \vec{\pi})$, the service of which should be interrupted to accept the target request, is determined from the recursive construction

$$b_{\hat{v}}(v, \vec{\pi}) = \min \left\{ F_R \left(\vec{e}_{\hat{v}} \left(\vec{\pi} - \vec{\Pi}_G \right) \right), F_R \left(\left[\frac{\vec{a} \left(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v - \vec{b}(v, \vec{\pi}) \right) - R}{\vec{a}\vec{e}_{\hat{v}}} \right] \right) \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{v} = V, \dots, 1$ and $F_R(x) = xF_H(x)$ is the Rampa function, transitively defined for the argument x through the Heaviside function $F_x(x)$. Note that $b_v(v, \bar{\pi}) = 0$, because of the conditions of a lack of network resources, the incoming request v cannot be accepted due to the interruption of already accepted target requests.

2.2. The concept of network resource control of a 5G cluster focused on the smart city's critical infrastructure needs

Let us present the access control scheme defined in Section 2.1 in the form of an V -dimensional stochastic process $\bar{X}(t) = (X_1(t), \dots, X_V(t))$ over the state space $\Psi = \{\bar{\pi} \in \mathbb{N}^V : (\bar{\pi} - \bar{\Pi}_{\max})\bar{e}^V \leq 0 \wedge \bar{\pi}\bar{a} \leq R\}$, where $t > 0$ and $X_v(t)$ is the number of accepted requests in the v -th network segment at time t , $v \in V$; \mathbb{N}^V is a set of vectors of length v , the elements of which are natural numbers; \bar{e}^V is a unit vector of length V .

We synchronize the space Ψ with the defined variants 1-3 of the implementation of the access control scheme by segmenting it into the following subsets:

- Ψ_v^{acc} is a set of states that characterize the situation when an incoming request to the network segment v will be accepted immediately:

$$\Psi_v^{acc} = \{\bar{\pi} \in \Psi : (\bar{\pi} - \bar{\Pi}_{\max})\bar{e}_v < 0 \wedge (\bar{\pi} + \bar{e}_v)\bar{a} \leq R\}; \quad (3)$$

- Ψ_v^{iacc} is a set of states that characterize the situation when an incoming request to a network segment v will be accepted due to the interruption of requests already accepted in network segments \hat{v} :

$$\Psi_v^{iacc} = \{\bar{\pi} \in \Psi : (\bar{\pi} - \bar{\Pi}_G)\bar{e}_v < 0 \wedge (\bar{\pi} + \bar{e}_v)\bar{a} \leq R\}; \quad (4)$$

- Ψ_v^{lost} is a set of states that characterize the situation when an incoming request to network segment v will be lost:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_v^{lost} &= \Psi \setminus (\Psi_v^{acc} \cup \Psi_v^{iacc}) \equiv \\ &\equiv \Psi_v^{lost} = \{\bar{\pi} \in \Psi : (\bar{\pi} - \bar{\Pi}_G)\bar{e}_v \geq 0 \wedge (\bar{\pi} + \bar{e}_v)\bar{a} > R\}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Let us structure the state space $\bar{\pi} \in \Psi$ of the stochastic process $\bar{X}(t)$, taking into account the defined subsets of Ψ_v^{acc} , Ψ_v^{iacc} , Ψ_v^{lost} :

- $\bigcap_{v \in V} \Psi_v^{acc}$ is a set of states that characterize the situation when the incoming request will be accepted immediately;
- $\bigcap_{v \in V} \Psi_v^{acc} \setminus \bigcup_{\hat{v} \in V \setminus \{v\}} \Psi_{\hat{v}}^{acc}$ is a set of states that characterize the situation when only the incoming request addressed to the network segment v will be accepted immediately;
- $\Psi_v^{iacc} \cap \bigcup_{\hat{v} \in V \setminus \{v\}} \Psi_{\hat{v}}^{iacc}$ is a set of states that characterize the situation when incoming requests addressed to network segments v and $\hat{v} \in V \setminus \{v\}$ will be accepted due to the interruption of already accepted requests in network segments $\tilde{v} \in V \setminus \{v, \hat{v}\}$;
- $\Psi_v^{iacc} \setminus \bigcup_{\hat{v} \in V \setminus \{v\}} \Psi_{\hat{v}}^{iacc}$ is a set of states that characterize the situation when an incoming request addressed to network segment v will be accepted due to the interruption of already accepted requests in network segments $\hat{v} \in V \setminus \{v\}$;
- $\bigcap_{v \in V} \Psi_v^{lost}$ is a set of states that characterize the situation when all incoming requests will be lost;
- $\Psi_v^{lost} \setminus \bigcup_{\hat{v} \in V \setminus \{v\}} \Psi_{\hat{v}}^{lost}$ is a set of states that characterize the situation when only incoming requests addressed to network segment v will be lost.

For clarity, we will present a certain way of structuring the space $\bar{\pi} \in \Psi$ in the form of a UML state diagram in Fig. 1. Elements of the mentioned in Fig. 1 vector $\bar{\eta} = (\eta_1, \dots, \eta_V)$ characterize the average service time of an accepted request in the corresponding network segment $v \in V$.

Figure 1. Scheme of structuring of space $\bar{\pi} \in \Psi \setminus \Psi_v^{lost}$.

In terms of expressions (3)-(5), we define the access control function as

$$f_v(\vec{\pi}) = \begin{cases} 1 \forall \vec{\pi} \in (\Psi_v^{acc} \cup \Psi_v^{iacc}), \\ 0 \forall \vec{\pi} \in \Psi_v^{lost}. \end{cases}$$

Let us present the one shown in Fig. 1 diagram analytically, in the form of a system of equilibrium equations:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\vec{\pi}) & \left(\bar{\mu} \sum_{v \in V} (I_{\Psi_v^{acc}}(\vec{\pi}) + I_{\Psi_v^{iacc}}(\vec{\pi})) \vec{e}_v + \vec{\pi} \vec{\eta} \right) = \\ & = \bar{\mu} \sum_{v \in V} (P(\vec{\pi} - \vec{e}_v) I_{\Psi_v^{acc}}(\vec{\pi} - \vec{e}_v) + \\ & + P(\vec{\pi} - \vec{e}_v + \vec{b}(v, \vec{\pi})) I_{\Psi_v^{iacc}}(\vec{\pi} - \vec{e}_v + \vec{b}(v, \vec{\pi})) \vec{e}_s + \\ & + \eta \sum_{v \in V} (P(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v) I_{\Psi_v^{acc}}(\vec{\pi}) (\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v) \vec{e}_v), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the stochastic values of the function $P(\vec{\pi} \in \Psi)$ ensure the equilibrium of the system of equations (6), and $I(\bullet)$ is an indexer function that allows us to take into account the priority of network segments.

The stochastic process $X(t)$, $t > 0$, which is reflected by the system of equilibrium equations (6), can be classified as an irreversible Markov process. Accordingly, the stationary probabilities $\vec{P} = (P(\vec{\pi}))$, $\vec{\pi} \in \Psi$, can be calculated, for example, using the Iterative Method [29]:

$$Q^T \vec{P} = 0, \quad \vec{P} \vec{e}^V = 1, \quad (7)$$

where Q is an infinitesimal matrix of dimension $\Psi \times \Psi$, the arbitrary $(\vec{\pi}, \vec{\bar{\pi}})$ -th element of which is defined as

$$Q(\vec{\pi}, \vec{\bar{\pi}}) = \begin{cases} \bar{\mu} \vec{e}_v \forall \vec{\pi} \in \Psi_v^{acc}, \vec{\bar{\pi}} = \vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v \vee \\ \vee \vec{\bar{\pi}} = \vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_v - \vec{b}(v, \vec{\pi}), \vec{\bar{\pi}} \in \Psi_v^{iacc}; \\ \vec{\pi} \vec{\eta} \vec{e}_v \forall \vec{\bar{\pi}} = \vec{\pi} - \vec{e}_v, \vec{\bar{\pi}} \in \Psi_v^{acc}; \\ 0 \forall \text{else}, \vec{\bar{\pi}} \in \Psi \setminus \{\vec{\pi}\}, \end{cases}$$

for $\vec{\pi} \in \Psi$, $\vec{\bar{\pi}} \in \Psi$, $\vec{\pi} \neq \vec{\bar{\pi}}$, and defined as

$$Q(\vec{\pi}, \vec{\bar{\pi}}) = \sum_{\vec{\bar{\pi}} \in \Psi \setminus \{\vec{\pi}\}} Q(\vec{\pi}, \vec{\bar{\pi}})$$

for $\vec{\pi} = \vec{\bar{\pi}}$.

The stationary probability distribution of states $\vec{\pi} \in \Psi \setminus \Psi^{lost}$ calculated according to (7) is the basis for the formalization of the main indicators of the effectiveness of the research object, namely:

- the average number of requests accepted for service:

$$\Pi = \sum_{\vec{\pi} \in \Psi} P(\vec{\pi}) \vec{\pi} \vec{e}^V; \quad (8)$$

- the probability of losing an incoming request:

$$P_{lost} = \sum_{\vec{\pi} \in L} P(\vec{\pi}), \quad L = \bigcap_{v=1}^V \Psi_v^{lost}; \quad (9)$$

- the average volume of used network resource units:

$$U = \sum_{\vec{\pi} \in \Psi} P(\vec{\pi}) \vec{\pi} \vec{a}. \quad (10)$$

2.3. Separate applied adaptations of the proposed concept

We will give examples of analytical adaptation of the concept proposed in Section 2.2 for cases when the communication resource of a 5G cluster is distributed between two or three network segments. The focus will be on determining the number of accepted non-targeted requests that should be interrupted to accept the targeted request at the expense of the guaranteed resource of the corresponding network segment (function (2)).

For this case $V = \{1, 2\}$, the state space $\vec{\pi} \in \Psi$ of the concept segmented into subsets (3)-(5) can be represented in 2D (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Graphical interpretation of the state space of a 5G cluster with two communication segments based on the proposed concept.

Let us determine the analytical form of the vector function of interruptions (2) for accepting the target request to the network segment 1: $\vec{b}(1, \vec{\pi}) = (b_1(1, \vec{\pi}), b_2(1, \vec{\pi}))$, with

$$\vec{\pi} = \left(\left\lfloor \frac{R}{a_1} \right\rfloor \left(1 - \frac{\lfloor R_2/a_2 \rfloor}{\lfloor R/a_2 \rfloor} \right), \left\lfloor \frac{R_2}{a_2} \right\rfloor \right). \quad (11)$$

According to Fig. 2, state (11) belongs to the set Ψ_1^{iacc} , i.e. the target request to the first network segment can be accepted only if the non-target requests accepted to the second network segment are interrupted.

Suppose that the studied 5G cluster is characterized by the following values of the initial parameters: $\vec{\lambda} \in \{1, \dots, 25\}$, $\mu_v = \lambda \eta_v$, $v=1 \vee 2$, $R=1.5$; $v=1$: $R_1=1.0$, $G_1=1.0$, $a_1=0.1$, $1/\eta_1=3600$; $v=2$: $R_2=0.5$, $G_2=0.5$, $a_2=0.4$, $1/\eta_2=1200$. Here R, G, a [Gbps], $1/\eta$ - [s]; $\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_v)$, where $\lambda_v \in \lambda$ is a parameter that characterizes the load of the network segment $v \in V$ with requests. Then, according to (11), we get $\vec{\pi} = (8, 16)$.

Now let's calculate the number of untargeted requests received in the second network segment $b_2(1, \vec{\pi})$, which should be interrupted to receive a target incoming request in the first network segment. With the initial value $\vec{b}(1, \vec{\pi}) = (0, 0)$, we will get

$$\begin{aligned} b_2(1, \vec{\pi}) &= \min \left\{ F_R \left(\vec{e}_2 \left(\vec{\pi} - \vec{\Pi}_G \right) \right), \right. \\ & \left. F_R \left(\left\lceil \frac{\vec{a} \left(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_1 \right) - R}{\vec{a} \vec{e}_2} \right\rceil \right) \right\} = \\ &= \min \{ F_R(4), F_R(1) \} = \min \{ 4, 1 \} = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Now let's determine the number of untargeted received requests in the first network segment $b_1(1, \vec{\pi})$, which should be interrupted to receive an incoming targeted request here. However, in Section 2.1 we discussed the condition that it is permissible to interrupt only accepted non-targeted requests in other network segments, not the one to which the targeted request is directed. Let's check whether the formulated mathematical apparatus reproduces this condition. Therefore, we have: $\vec{b}(1, \vec{\pi}) = (0, b_2(1, \vec{\pi}) = 1)$. Taking this equality into account, we get

$$\begin{aligned} b_1(1, \vec{\pi}) &= \min \left\{ F_R \left(\vec{e}_1 \left(\vec{\pi} - \vec{\Pi}_G \right) \right), \right. \\ & \left. F_R \left(\left\lceil \frac{\vec{a} \left(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_1 - \vec{b}(1, \vec{\pi}) \right) - R}{\vec{a} \vec{e}_1} \right\rceil \right) \right\} = \\ &= \min \{ F_R(-2), F_R(0) \} = \min \{ 0, 0 \} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Therefore, for the state $\vec{\pi} = (8,16)$, the vector function of interruptions (2) is defined as $\vec{b}(1, \vec{\pi}) = (b_1(1, \vec{\pi}), b_2(1, \vec{\pi}))$. By substituting the found values (13), and (12) into $\vec{b}(1, \vec{\pi})$, we get $\vec{z}(1, \vec{\pi}) = (0,1)$. This means that for the assumed initial conditions for the investigated 5G cluster with two network segments, to receive a target request in the first segment, one received a non-target request in the second network segment will have to be interrupted.

Now let's assume that the 5G cluster, the communication resource of which is divided between three network segments $V = \{1,2,3\}$, is characterized by the following values of the initial parameters: $R = 13$, $\vec{a} = (1,3,1)$, $\vec{\pi} = (6,1,4)$, $\vec{\Pi}_G = (2,2,2)$. Let's define the vector function (2) for accepting the target incoming request in the second network segment: $v = 2$. In terms of the interruption function (2), this problem is formulated as $\vec{b}(2, \vec{\pi}) = (b_1(2, \vec{\pi}), b_2(2, \vec{\pi}), b_3(2, \vec{\pi}))$, $\vec{\pi} \in \Psi_2^{iacc}$. The initial condition is $\vec{b}(2, \vec{\pi}) = (0,0,0)$. We remember that the index of a network segment characterizes its priority – as the index increases, the priority decreases.

Let's determine the number of accepted non-targeted requests in the third network segment $b_3(2, \vec{\pi})$, which should be interrupted to accept one targeted incoming request in the guaranteed resource space of the second network segment:

$$\begin{aligned} b_3(2, \vec{\pi}) &= \min \left\{ F_R \left(\vec{e}_3 \left(\vec{\pi} - \vec{\Pi}_G \right) \right), \right. \\ & \left. F_R \left(\left[\frac{\vec{a} \left(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_2 \right) - R}{\vec{e}_3 \vec{a}} \right] \right) \right\} = \\ &= \min \{ F_R(2), F_R(3) \} = \min \{ 2, 3 \} = 2. \end{aligned}$$

The concept described in Section 2.2 was formed under the condition that it is not possible to interrupt received requests in the network segment to which the target incoming request is directed. Let's make sure of this by defining the function $b_2(2, \vec{\pi})$ for $\vec{b}(0,0, b_3(2, \vec{\pi}) = 2)$:

$$\begin{aligned} b_2(2, \vec{\pi}) &= \min \left\{ F_R \left(\vec{e}_3 \left(\vec{\pi} - \vec{\Pi}_G \right) \right), \right. \\ & \left. F_R \left(\left[\frac{\vec{a} \left(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_2 - \vec{b}(2, \vec{\pi}) \right) - R}{\vec{e}_2 \vec{a}} \right] \right) \right\} = \\ &= \min \{ F_R(-1), F_R(1) \} = \min \{ 0, 1 \} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

In contrast to similar concepts, our proposed one provides the possibility of interrupting received non-targeted requests in network segments with a priority higher than the priority of the network segment to which the target incoming request is directed (in our example, the network segment with index 1 has a higher priority than network segment 2, to which the incoming request is directed). Let's make sure of this by defining the function $b_1(2, \vec{\pi})$ for $\vec{b}(0, b_2(2, \vec{\pi}) = 0, b_3(2, \vec{\pi}) = 2)$:

$$\begin{aligned} b_1(2, \vec{\pi}) &= \min \left\{ F_R \left(\vec{e}_1 \left(\vec{\pi} - \vec{\Pi}_G \right) \right), \right. \\ & \left. F_R \left(\left[\frac{\vec{a} \left(\vec{\pi} + \vec{e}_2 - \vec{b}(2, \vec{\pi}) \right) - R}{\vec{e}_1 \vec{a}} \right] \right) \right\} = \\ &= \min \{ F_R(4), F_R(1) \} = \min \{ 4, 1 \} = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, for the state $\vec{\pi} = (6,1,4)$, $\vec{\pi} \in \Psi_2^{iacc}$, the vector of interruptions (2) has the form $\vec{b}(2, \vec{\pi}) = (b_1(2, \vec{\pi}), b_2(2, \vec{\pi}), b_3(2, \vec{\pi})) = (1,0,2)$. That is, to receive a targeted incoming request in the second network segment, one received non-price request in the first network segment and two received non-targeted requests in the third network segment will have to be interrupted.

3. Results

Let's prove the effectiveness of the proposed interrupt control concept (Interrupt Control Scheme, ICS) in the 5G cluster empirically by comparing the author's development with the most commonly used network resource control scheme with redundancy (Redundant Control Scheme, RCS) [16-18]. For an adequate comparison, we will present the results of the experiments in the metric of qualitative indicators (8)-(10), where indicator (8) characterizes the average number of received requests in the cluster Π , indicator (9) characterizes the probability of losing an incoming request P_{lost} , indicator (10) characterizes the average volume of network resource units involved in the cluster U .

We define the input data for modelling as follows:

$V = 4$:

$v = 1$ (3K VR): ICS: $R_1 = 1.0; G_1 = 1.0; a_1 = 0.1; 1/\eta_1 = 3600$, RCS: $R_1 = 1.25; G_1 = 1.0; a_1 = 0.1; 1/\eta_1 = 3600$;

$v = 2$ (4K Video 30 fps): ICS: $R_2 = 0.5; G_2 = 0.5; a_2 = 0.4; 1/\eta_2 = 1200$, RCS: $R_2 = 0.65; G_2 = 0.5; a_2 = 0.4; 1/\eta_2 = 1200$;

$v = 3$ (4K Video 25 fps): ICS: $R_3 = 0.5; G_3 = 0.5; a_3 = 0.03; 1/\eta_3 = 1800$, RCS: $R_3 = 0.65; G_3 = 0.5; a_3 = 0.03; 1/\eta_3 = 1800$;

$v = 4$ (4K Video 60 fps): ICS: $R_4 = 0.5; G_4 = 0.5; a_4 = 0.063; 1/\eta_4 = 5400$, RCS: $R_3 = 0.65; G_3 = 0.5; a_3 = 0.03; 1/\eta_3 = 1800$;
 R, G, a [Gbps], $1/\eta$ - [s].

Then, at $\lambda = (1, \dots, 25)$, $\mu_v = \lambda \eta_v$ [request per second], network segments were activated according to the following scenarios:

Action1: $R = 1.5, V = (1, 2)$;

Action2: $R = 2.0, V = (2, 3)$;

Action3: $R = 2.5, V = (1, 2, 3, 4)$.

For the initial conditions presented above (including $\langle \text{ICS}, \text{RCS} \rangle$, $\langle \text{Action1}, \dots, \text{Action3} \rangle$), we determine the dependence of the values of the metric indicators $\langle \Pi, P_{lost}, U \rangle$, defined by equations (8)-(10), on the intensity of the load $\lambda_v \in \lambda$ applied to each v -th network segment. The results of the calculations are shown in Fig. 3-5, respectively.

Figure 3. Dependence of $\Pi = f(\lambda)$ on $\{\text{ICS}, \text{RCS}\}$ and $\{\text{action1}, \dots, \text{action3}\}$.

Figure 4. Dependence of $P_{lost} = f(\lambda)$ on $\{\text{ICS}, \text{RCS}\}$ and $\{\text{action1}, \dots, \text{action3}\}$.

Figure 5. Dependence of $U = f(\lambda)$ on $\{\text{ICS,RCS}\}$ and $\{\text{action1},\dots,\text{action3}\}$.

Fig. 3-5 represents the directly calculated values of the metric $\langle \Pi, P_{lost}, U \rangle$ under the specified conditions. However, if there is a need to compare access control schemes $\langle \text{ICS,RCS} \rangle$, then it is advisable to switch to the relative metric $\langle \Pi_{ICS} / \Pi_{RCS}, P_{lost}^{ICS} / P_{lost}^{RCS}, U_{ICS} / U_{RCS} \rangle$. Such an interpretation is not only normalized concerning the scheme ICS but also allows focusing on the averaged influence of the access control scheme on the efficiency of the functioning of the 5G cluster, the information environment of which is organized according to scenarios $\langle \text{Action1}, \dots, \text{Action3} \rangle$. The results of the corresponding calculations are presented in Fig. 6-8.

Figure 6. Dependence of $\Pi_{ICS} / \Pi_{RCS} = f(\lambda)$ on $\{\text{action1},\dots,\text{action3}\}$.

Figure 7. Dependence of $P_{lost}^{ICS} / P_{lost}^{RCS} = f(\lambda)$ on $\{\text{action1},\dots,\text{action3}\}$.

Figure 8. Dependence of $U_{ICS}/U_{RCS} = f(\lambda)$ on $\{\text{action1}, \dots, \text{action3}\}$.

4. Discussion

Let's sequentially analyze the obtained experimental results by grouping in pairs Fig. 3 and Fig. 6 ($\Pi = f(\lambda)$ and $\Pi_{ICS}/\Pi_{RCS} = f(\lambda)$), Fig. 4 and Fig. 7 ($P_{lost} = f(\lambda)$ and $P_{lost}^{ICS}/P_{lost}^{RCS} = f(\lambda)$), Fig. 5 and Fig. 8 ($U = f(\lambda)$ and $U_{ICS}/U_{RCS} = f(\lambda)$). This is logical because certain pairs of figures complement each other.

So, Fig. 3 and Fig. 6 are devoted to the qualitative indicator (8), which characterizes the average number of received requests in the studied 5G cluster. Fig. 3 shows that as the load on the network segments of the 5G cluster increases, the average number of received requests in the studied cluster increases for all access control schemes $\langle \text{ICS}, \text{RCS} \rangle$ and options for implementing network segments $\langle \text{Action1}, \dots, \text{Action3} \rangle$. Note that the growth dynamics of the graphs in Fig. 3 are nonlinear, but not exponential either. This result is a consequence of the correspondence of the given values of the initial parameters regarding the resource availability of the 5G cluster to the selected range of variation of the load values λ . The author's access control scheme outperforms the known competitor over the entire range of argument values and for all configurations of the network segment structure in the 5G cluster $\langle \text{Action1}, \dots, \text{Action3} \rangle$. We can also state that with the increase in the number of network segments (Action3 compared to Action1 and Action2) and their resource availability (Action2 compared to Action1), the average number of accepted requests in the 5G cluster increases. Graphs from Fig. 6 complement the conclusions made. However, note that the functions $\Pi_{ICS}/\Pi_{RCS} = f(\lambda)$ for all $\langle \text{Action1}, \dots, \text{Action3} \rangle$ have a pronounced extremum for the values of load $10 < \lambda < 15$. This allows us to conclude that the author's scheme ICS outperforms the competitor RCS for relatively low values of load λ . It can be expected that as $\lambda \gg 25$ increases, schemes ICS and RCS will reach parity in terms of the quality metric Π_{ICS}/Π_{RCS} .

Fig. 4 and Fig. 7 are devoted to the qualitative indicator (9), which characterizes the probability of losing an incoming request (the less, the better). From Fig. 4, it can be seen that as the load λ increases, the value of the metric P_{lost} increases for all configurations of the 5G cluster structure imposed by $\langle \text{Action1}, \dots, \text{Action3} \rangle$. Moreover, the growth rate increases with the increase in the number of network segments (for the scenario Action3, the growth rate of the graph $P_{lost} = f(\lambda)$ is the highest). Interestingly, the general trends are common to both scheme ICS and scheme RCS. However, it should be noted the noticeable advantage of the scheme RCS with the same scenarios $\langle \text{Action1}, \dots, \text{Action3} \rangle$. The analysis of graphs from Fig. 7 allows the predominance of a scheme RCS to be slightly shaken. We see that the ratio $P_{lost}^{ICS}/P_{lost}^{RCS}$ is less than unity for scenarios Action2 and Action3 for the range of the argument $1 < \lambda < 4.50$, i.e., again, at low values of load.

Finally, Fig. 5 and Fig. 8 are devoted to the qualitative indicator (10), which characterizes the average volume of used network resource units in the cluster. From Fig. 5, it can be seen that the author's scheme ICS allows more dense use of the prepaid network resources of the 5G cluster. Moreover, as the number of network segments increases, this advantage increases: $U = f(\lambda, \text{Action3}) \gg U = f(\lambda, \text{Action1})$ at $\lambda > 3$. However, the graphs from Fig. 8 allow us to conclude that this advantage is the highest in the $7 < \lambda < 12$ range, that is, in the range of low loads on the 5G cluster.

Summing up, we will say that Fig. 3-5 allowed us to determine the trends regarding the effectiveness of the investigated control schemes for the specified initial conditions, while Fig. 6-8 allowed us to establish ranges where this effectiveness is undeniable. It can be stated that the author's scheme ICS outperforms the competitor RCS in the range of low loads (for the studied implementation of the 5G cluster, this is the range $1 < \lambda < 12$). Moreover, we note that in this range the advantage of the author's scheme over the competitor increases significantly with the increase in the number of network segments into which the information environment of the 5G cluster is divided.

5. Conclusions

In modern agglomerations, wireless communication providers work in conditions of oversaturated allowed frequency range. At the same time, information exchange in the sector of critical urban infrastructure is actively increasing. These conflicting realities form a paradox, which is the basis of the scientific problem of controlling the network resources of a 5G cluster focused on the smart city's critical infrastructure needs.

The article proposes a concept of organizing access to the guaranteed resource of the 5G cluster information environment, structured in the form of a hierarchy of logical network segments. This framework presents an interrupt access control scheme that exhibits survivability characteristics important to mission-critical applications. It is understood that to accept a target request in a network segment, it is allowed to interrupt accepted non-target requests in other network segments, regardless of the priority index of the latter. Analytically, the author's concept is represented by an irreversible Markov process, for which a system of equilibrium equations and stationary probabilities are defined. Based on the latter, a qualitative metric was formulated, which included such indicators as the average number of requests accepted for service in the 5G cluster, the probability of losing an incoming request, and the average volume of network resource units used in the 5G cluster.

For the single input data that characterizes a real NS 5G cluster, a comparison of the author's and known competing access control schemes in terms of formulated qualitative metrics is implemented. The obtained results showed that the author's concept prevails over the competitor in the range of low loads. Note that in this range, the advantage of the author's scheme over the competitor significantly increases with the increase in the number of network segments into which the information environment of the 5G cluster is divided.

Further research is planned to focus on mitigating the identified limitations of the author's concept. This means a faster growth in the number of unaccepted input requests compared to competitors with increasing load on the 5G cluster.

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